

TECHNOLOGY OF INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF STUDENTS' PHYSICAL FITNESS WITH THE HELP OF (FITNESS EXERCISES) MEANS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT SCHOOL

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Abstract. *Methodical ways of the process of creating a technology for increasing the effectiveness of physical education of schoolchildren with the help of physical education means (fitness exercises) were determined and the improvement of the effectiveness of physical training of schoolchildren was achieved.*

Keywords: *fitness exercises, aerobics, innovative technology, efficiency of exercise, Physical development, physical training, physical exercise, physical qualities mobility.*

INTRODUCTION

Health is the basis of a person's life, well-being, work activity, creative success and longevity. It reflects the standard of living and well-being of the country, has a direct impact on labor productivity, defense ability, moral principles of society, and people's mood. Interest in physical education remains high. This indicates that health-improving physical culture, which considers human health to be in close relationship with the level of movement and lifestyle, is becoming one of the priorities in the life of a modern person. Modern physical culture and health technologies, including the expansion of knowledge that can be used at school.

"Healthy physical culture" is a derivative of the generalized concept. Health-enhancing physical education uses all forms, means and methods of physical education that ensure strengthening and maintenance of health and create an optimal environment for human health. The task of health-improving physical culture is to improve general health, to increase the body's resistance to harmful environmental influences, to prevent diseases, etc. Health fitness classes do not aim to achieve any sports results or cure diseases (as in physical therapy) and are available to all practical healthy people. At least three aspects can be distinguished in a healthy physical culture: activity, subjective value and effectiveness. Let's look at the main terms and concepts used with the quality of physical culture and wellness: physical culture and wellness technology, physical culture and wellness activities, physical culture and wellness work, physical culture and wellness activity, physical culture and health system. In fact, the technology of physical culture and wellness is a method of implementing activities aimed at achieving and maintaining physical well-being and reducing the risk of developing diseases through physical culture and wellness. These are the basic rules for the use of special knowledge and skills, the methods of organizing and carrying out specific actions necessary to perform physical culture and recreational activities. Any physical culture and wellness technology includes setting goals and tasks of wellness, actual implementation of physical culture and wellness activities in one form or another.

Technology includes not only the implementation of a healthy lifestyle program, but also health assessment and fitness testing, as well as administration and management issues. Thus, physical culture and wellness technology is a method of implementing various physical culture and wellness activities. This is the basis of the health industry and the so-called physical education and health work. Means of improving physical culture and public orientation The principle of health-oriented physical education of the population is concretized in the currently rapidly developing physical culture and healthcare technologies. The concept of physical culture and wellness technology combines the process of using physical education tools for recreation and the scientific discipline that develops and improves the foundations of the methodology of building the physical culture and wellness process. Fitness programs and their classification Motor activity organized within a special group or individual (personal) classes, as a form of Fitness programs, health-training direction (reducing the risk of developing diseases, and maintaining the correct level of physical condition) , can also be, and at a sufficiently high level is related to the development of the ability to solve motor and sports tasks. The classification of fitness programs is based on the following: a) a type of motor activity (for example, aerobics, fitness running, swimming, etc.); b) on combining several types of motor activity (for example, aerobics and bodybuilding; aerobics and stretching; recreational swimming and running, etc.); c) one or more types of motor activity and various factors of a healthy lifestyle (for example, aerobics and fitness; bodybuilding and massage; recreational swimming and a complex of hydrotherapy restorative procedures, etc.). In turn, fitness programs based on one type of motor activity are types of aerobic motor activity; fitness types of gymnastics; types of power-oriented motor activity; types of motor activity in water; recreational types of car activity; can be divided into programs based on psych emotional regulation tools. Such a variety of fitness programs is determined by the desire to satisfy the interests of the general population in terms of physical culture and fitness.

The content of the concept of fitness includes multifactorial components (physical fitness, rational nutrition, disease prevention, social activity, including stress management and other factors of a healthy lifestyle), the number of created fitness programs is almost unlimited. The structure and content of fitness programs. The diversity of fitness programs does not mean that their construction is arbitrary - the use of various types of motor activities should be consistent with the basic principles of physical education. An important component of modern fitness programs is a system of special fixed positions of certain parts of the body to improve muscle elasticity and develop joint mobility. Physical exercises at the end of the aerobic or strength part, as well as in the form of independent exercises, compression exercises reduce excessive neuropsychiatric tension, eliminate the syndrome of delayed muscle pain after exercise, and serve as prevention of injury after the main heat.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

At the beginning of the 20th century, Russian philosophers, teachers, doctors made a great contribution to the formation of knowledge about the benefits of physical exercises for health promotion and recovery: N.A.Berdyayev, N.I.Pirogov, D.I.Pisarev, K.D.Ushinsky, P.F.Lesgaft, A.S.Makarenko, I.M.Sechenov and others.

The representatives of the National Knowledge Formation School emphasized the special importance of one of the important features of improving human activity through tools. As stated by P.F. Lesgaft, it is necessary to distinguish between "big sport" and physical education, the latter should only improve health. The rules put forward by him about the need to focus on the healthy

direction of physical exercises used in physical education, the personal needs and interests of the participants, the development of amateur initiatives serve as the basis for creating the theory of healthy physical culture. The simultaneous development of elite sports (the country's prestige in the international arena), the introduction of "Physical culture" into the curricula of all educational institutions, the introduction of physical recreation and physical rehabilitation into everyday life - all this was required.

During these years, in our country, against the background of the rise of physical education and sports activities, a healthy physical culture is also developing, and innovative healthy author's methods and systems, which are often named after their creator, appeared (P.K. Ivanov system; G.S. Shatalova). system; N.M.Amosov's fitness exercise system, A. Strelnikova's breathing exercises, etc.).

The common aspect of such methods and systems is that they mainly involve factors: nutrition; heat factor (exercise - air baths, walking, stones, sand, snow; sun; swimming; bath, sauna). Rapid development of healthy physical culture and the popularization of gymnastics give a certain impetus to the emergence of its healthy types. At the end of this period, the following areas: artistic, athletic, women's gymnastics; as well as eastern directions: yoga, wushu, etc., at the same time psych regulation and autogenic training methods are also developing. At the moment, cyclic types of physical activity are becoming popular - healthy walking, running, swimming, cycling, etc. Thus, we can say that fitness has all the characteristic features that allow it to be defined as a novelty at the current stage of the development of physical culture. At the same time, in our opinion, it can be noted that it is firmly based on the ideas, traditions, means, methods, and forms of traditional physical culture. He mastered them, filled them with new content, updated existing approaches to their application.

The emergence and development of fitness was intended to contribute to the achievement of the goals of strengthening health, increasing the physical capabilities of people and introducing them to physical education.

RESULTS

Currently, many innovative technologies, methods and health programs are being developed in the physical education system.

This predetermined the emergence of new terms in the theory and practice of physical culture: "pedagogical technologies", "technology improvement", "innovative technologies", "health technologies", "fitness technologies" and others.

To solve the most urgent task of modern local physical culture - to improve people's health and increase interest in physical education thanks to attractive and modern teaching directions, inventory, equipment and related factors.

In physical education classes, physical education tools are used to solve educational, educational and health problems in accordance with the requirements of the program. In the educational process, various collective physical education means are used from Each of the physical training means should solve its own educational, educational and health-improving tasks. The tasks mentioned above are closely related to each other. When solving them, it is necessary to take into account various aspects of the educational process. Similarly, to improve agility during fitness training, students can develop courage, intelligence, and self-confidence at the same time. The difference between exercises in physical education classes and other forms of training is that the most important thing is to pay attention to the educational and health aspects of the exercises,

as well as to the quality of physical education. When choosing an exercise for a lesson, consider the task of the lesson, educational material, it is necessary to consider the physiological load of the exercise, the conditions for work. In each exercise requires participants to demonstrate their knowledge and skills, and improves them during training. Elementary exercises do not require special preparation. However, there are exercises that consist of complex movements.

Participants master complex movements included in fitness exercises with the help of special exercises. As an exception, there may be elementary and medical actions that do not require prior training. Fitness exercises can be included in all parts of the lesson. It is recommended to include low-motion and uncomplicated fitness exercises in the preparation of the lesson, which will help students to focus, as well as exercises of a general development nature performed with moderate-motion fitness exercises. The specificity of the methodology of conducting fitness exercises in the physical education class is related to the need to maintain the intensity of the class and its short duration. Appropriate use of time and proper selection of the method of conducting fitness exercises will achieve the necessary intensity in the lesson. To achieve this, all students receive roughly the same load. It should try to create equal conditions for active participation of all those involved in this. In order to train boys to develop endurance and strength, girls are given exercises that train coordination skills. It is necessary to set a certain time for doing the exercises. Because it can be related to students' fatigue, insufficient mastery of the exercise, and other reasons. Such exercises are numerous and complex, and students are required to have agility, endurance, perseverance and patience in solving the exercises.

In the course of our research, we will have to interest the students of school No. 24 with the help of fitness exercises through the technology of increasing the effectiveness of the physical education lesson, and bring them into this environment. We should use fitness exercises to increase the effectiveness of physical education classes.

In order to develop speed

Complex 1

1. I/P Legs apart, hands down. Turning the head back and forth.
2. I/P Legs apart, hands down. Tilt the head to the left, to the right.
3. I/P Stand with feet apart, swing both arms up and down.
4. I/P Keep the legs apart, swing up and down to the sides with both hands.
5. I/P Feet shoulder width apart, hands behind your head. The body bends left and right.
6. I/P Feet shoulder width apart, hands on the belt. Circular movements of the pelvis.
7. I/P Wide stand. Circular movements of the body alternately left and right.
8. I/P Keep your legs apart. Bending of the body to the left, forward, to the right leg.
9. I/P Keep your legs apart. Raise the leg bent at the knee joint and cross it to the side.

Also the other leg.

10. I/P Keep your legs apart. Mahi's free leg to the side.
11. I/P Basic posture. Circular movements in the knee joints.
12. I/P Basic posture. Circular movements in the ankle joints.
13. I/P Feet shoulder width apart. 4-left, 4-right, 8-double jump.
14. Walking: 1. Shaking hands (making a fist, separating fingers, etc.).

* **I/P**- Initial Position

Indicators of development of physical qualities
The results of the test on the development of physical qualities with 7^B-grade students
(Control group)

No	Students' names and surnames	60-meter run		Turnstiles (boys), bending the body (girls) (times)		1500m (Boys) 1000m (Girls) (min.sec)		run 4x.10m (seconds)		forward bend while standing on a bench, (sm)	
		Research before	Research after	Research before	After research	Before the study	Research after	Research before	Research after	Research before	Research after
1	A. A	10.2	10.0	6	7	8.54	5.44	8.8	7.8	9	7
2	A. Sh	13.6	13.1	6	6	9.50	7.50	7.9	.9	8	8
3	B. S	10.8	10.8	7	8	8.48	8.48	9.6	9.6	7	5
4	D. K	14.8	14.8	5	5	7.44	7.44	11.4	11.4	8	8
5	E. B	13.5	13.5	4	4	8.42	6.42	9.4	9.4	8	8
6	E. Z	13.6	13.4	7	7	9.50	9.50	10.4	8.4	8	8
7	F. F	12.4	12.4	6	7	10.46	9.40	8.6	8.6	9	9
8	B. D	14.8	14.8	5	5	9.50	9.50	9.5	9.5	10	9
9	J. A	18.5	17.2	4	4	9.20	9.20	9.6	9.6	8	8
10	J. D	14.2	14.2	6	6	9.18	9.18	8.6	8.6	9	9
11	K. S	16.6	16.0	8	8	10.15	9.15	12.4	9.4	10	8
12	M. H	14.6	14.6	10	11	8.17	8.17	12.6	12.6	8	8
13	M. T	16.8	16.8	8	8	9.18	9.18	9.6	9.6	12	12
14	M. S	14.4	14.4	6	6	9.20	9.20	8.6	8.6	4	4
15	M. S	10.4	10.4	6	6	8.17	7.17	10.2	10.2	8	8
16	N. F	12.8	12.8	7	7	8.20	8.20	10.6	9.6	9	9
17	N. J	10.2	10.2	4	4	9.55	9.55	9.8	9.8	8	8
18	Q. J	13.4	13.4	5	5	5.42	5.42	9.2	9.2	10	10
19	Q. U	12.8	12.8	3	3	5.44	8.54	9.8	9.8	9	7
20	T. J	14.6	14.6	8	8	5.40	5.40	9.0	9.0	8	8
21	S. V	13.4	13.4	2	2	5.37	5.37	9.0	9.0	10	8
22	X. A	15.4	15.4	4	4	5.57	5.57	9.6	7.6	5	5
23	B. D	18.2	17.2	12	12	7.42	7.42	10.8	10.8	9	9
24	I. S	15.6	15.6	13	13	8.40	8.40	8.8	8.8	9	9
25	S. S	17.6	17.6	14	14	9.39	9.39	10.6	9.6	14	10
26	D. A	16.6	16.6	12	12	8.41	8.41	11.6	11.6	12	12
27	M. Z	14.4	14.4	10	10	9.45	9.45	12.7	12.7	10	10
28	M.	17.6	16.2	10	10	8.28	8.28	10.4	9.4	14	10
29	N.	15.4	15.4	8	8	7.30	6.30	9.6	9.6	9	9
30	U. K	16.7	16.7	12	10	8.31	8.31	12.4	12.4	8	8
31	R. G	15.9	14.2	16	15	8.29	8.29	10.6	10.6	9	9
32	T. B	14.3	14.3	5	5	9.38	9.38	12.2	9.2	10	10
33	U. Z	15.6	15.6	6	6	10.50	9.50	11.4	11.4	12	9
34	X. L	11.4	11.2	10	10	12.42	10.42	10.6	9.6	10	8
	X - Average	13.7	<u>14</u>	7.1	<u>7</u>	7.9	<u>7.7</u>	9.6	<u>9.4</u>	8.9	<u>8.6</u>

**The results of the test on the development of physical qualities with 7^A-class students.
 (Experimental group)**

No	Students' names and surnames	60-meter run, (sec)		Turnstiles (boys), bending the body (girls) times		1500m (Boys) 1000 m(Girls) min. sec		run to 4x.10 m (seconds)		forward bend while standing on a bench, sm	
		Before the study	After research	Before the study	After research	Before the study	After research	Before the study	After research	Before the study	After research
1	A. A	9.10	9.2	5	7	7.54	7.40	9.8	9.6	9	7
2	A. I	10.4	10.0	5	8	7.50	7.43	9.9	9.6	6	5
3	A. M	11.6	10.5	7	9	7.48	7.45	8.6	8.2	8	7
4	Sh. J	10.6	10.0	8	10	7.44	7.13	10.4	10.0	5	4
5	B. A	9.9	9.0	4	5	7.42	6.39	9.4	9.0	9	8
6	B. U	10.4	10.0	2	5	7.50	7.47	10.4	10.0	12	11
7	E. A	11.8	11.2	8	9	7.46	7.38	8.6	7.8	10	9
8	E. Z	13.0	12.2	9	10	7.50	7.30	8.5	8.2	9	8
9	H. Sh	10.4	10.0	5	6	6.20	6.10	9.6	9.0	8	7
10	J. N	9.5	9.2	8	9	6.18	6.16	8.6	8.2	6	5
11	K. I	9.9	9.1	3	5	6.15	6.17	12.4	12.0	8	7
12	M. F	13.6	12.4	2	5	6.17	6.12	10.6	9.8	9	8
13	M. S	10.4	10.0	4	5	6.18	6.14	9.6	9.0	7	6
14	M. D	11.6	10.5	4	5	6.20	6.17	12.6	11.0	11	10
15	M. O	12.6	11.6	5	6	6.17	6.12	10.2	10.0	9	7
16	Q. Sh	10.4	9.50	6	7	6.20	6.13	14.6	11.2	5	4
17	Y. Z	10.4	10.2	5	5	5.55	5.40	9.8	9.0	5	5
18	Q. A	9.9	9.8	4	5	5.42	4.41	9.2	9.0	7	6
19	K. S	10.8	10.4	3	4	5.44	5.42	9.8	9.0	6	4
20	R.S	14.8	12.2	5	6	5.40	5.38	9.0	8.2	7	6
21	R. R	10.4	9.40	6	7	5.37	4.00	9.0	8.8	8	7
22	S. Kh	12.6	11.30	8	9	5.57	5.50	9.6	9.0	6	5
23	X. A	10.4	10.0	2	5	5.42	5.39	10.8	10.0	4	3
24	O. R	9.9	9.4	5	7	5.40	5.37	8.8	8.6	6	5
25	S. O	13.8	12.5	6	7	5.39	5.36	10.6	9.0	8	4
26	T. O	10.4	10.2	7	9	5.41	5.38	13.6	12.0	5	3
27	Y. O	12.2	12.0	8	9	5.45	5.40	12.7	12.2	8	7
28	A. D	14.8	12.2	12	11	6.28	5.26	10.4	10.0	10	9
29	U. M	10.4	10.0	10	9	6.30	6.28	11.6	11.2	11	8
30	Y. S	9.9	9.2	8	9	6.31	5.27	12.4	11.6	5	4
31	S. G	10.5	10.0	8	9	6.29	6.24	9.6	9.0	16	14
32	X. Y	14.8	14.0	10	11	6.38	6.30	14.2	14.0	9	8
33	S. M	10.9	10.0	12	12	6.50	6.12	10.4	10.0	15	12
34	Q. L	16.8	16.0	12	13	6.42	6.40	12.6	11.2	15	13
35	M. A	16.4	16.1	15	15	6.20	6.18	9.6	9.0	8	7
36	R. D	13.8	13.2	15	16	6.24	6.22	9.4	9.0	22	18
	X - Average	11.3	10	6.7	8.1	6.2	6.0	10.4	9.2	8.5	7.3

Determination of physical indicators of 7th grade students before and after the experiment.

n-36

No	Name and surname	60- m run		Turnstile (boys), bending the body (girls)		1500m (Boys) 1000 m(Girls) (min. sec)		run to 4x.10 m (seconds)		forward bend while standing on a bench, (sm)	
		Before	Then	Before	Then	Before	Then	Before	Then	Before	Then
1	Control group	13.7	<u>14</u>	7.1	<u>7</u>	7.9	<u>7.7</u>	9.6	<u>9.4</u>	8.9	<u>8.6</u>
2	Experience group	11.3	<u>10</u>	6.7	<u>8.1</u>	6.2	<u>6.0</u>	10.4	<u>9.2</u>	8.5	<u>7.3</u>

Conclusion. This article presents pedagogical experimental materials aimed at determining the level of effectiveness of the use of fitness exercises planned according to the development of the qualities of speed and agility of students according to the technology of increasing the effectiveness of physical education lessons of schoolchildren with the help of physical education tools (fitness exercises) at school.

Pedagogical studies of 14-15-year-old children in different age, gender groups made it possible to determine not only the characteristics of the influence of pedagogical experience on the process of improvement of various physical qualities, but also the age characteristics of their changes.

Pedagogical experience has shown that it is possible not only to preserve the natural age characteristics characteristic of changes in all physical qualities, but in some cases even to accelerate these processes. It's more about agility and quickness, and less about endurance, strength, and flexibility. Data indicating a clearly expressed heterochronic reaction of the locomotor apparatus to the effects of individual physical exercises were obtained. It was shown that even in the analysis of changes in one or another physical quality on the basis of different test tasks, the level of reliability was very different, in some cases the coefficient of variation reached 80%; this is often the case of the body of school-aged students acceleration process, especially during the acceleration of the development of the neuromuscular apparatus, allows us to talk about the strong influence of a number of mechanisms in functional systems that limit the importance of physical exercise. It is clear that the neuromuscular apparatus of 14-15-year-old students is not yet mature, it is in the stage of rapid formation. In addition, it is necessary to pay attention to this phenomenon: children of this age have distinct age-gender characteristics.

The analysis of the interaction of physical qualities in dependence made it possible to understand the essence of the changes that occurred as a result of pedagogical experience. If we draw a straight line under these studies, we can say with high confidence that it is possible to seriously increase the number of reliable connections between the physical qualities of schoolchildren due to pedagogical experience.

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